

open DOORS - Designing a network of cOOperating cReative communities for developing a Sharing economy

Interreg MED Programme

Priority Axis 1: Promoting Mediterranean innovation capacities to develop smart and sustainable growth

Specific objective: 1.1 To increase transnational activity of innovative clusters and networks of key sectors of the MED area

Map of resources

Map of resources

Open DOORS project

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1. Introduction

The databases of Platforms, Stakeholders and Laws were already designed and provided by CNR in the deliverable D3.3.1. Each stakeholder can register herself/himself in this database (meaning actors representative for a platform, or policy makers interested in disseminating new laws or regulations, or scientists, as well as civil society organizations interested in the sharing and collaborative economy) and, can upload new information or update the existing one. This enables each new Stakeholder, Platform or Law to be indexed, allowing to reinforce the networking concept important to evolve sharing and collaborative approaches for an innovative, sustainable and inclusive society. This open approach was decided coherently with the Open DOORS project purpose of “Creating a Network of Cooperating Creative Communities for Developing a Sharing Economy” as the Declaration of Valencia affirms: The declaration of Valencia is available at:

<https://www.uv.es/econcult/pdf/2017%20OPENDOORS%20DECLARATION%20OF%20VALENCIA.pdf>

Information on Stakeholder, Platform or Law, collected in the database can be visualised on a map.

Note that, when people get connected, they can visualise locations with which platforms, stakeholders and laws are related to, and then to access to specific information.

Moreover, a repository of documents and websites related to the sharing and the collaborative economy has been created, following the suggestions of the partnership and some stakeholders’ suggestions during the project activities.

People, who are interested in uploading information in the databases or in the collection of documents, can contribute after their registration in the website containing the map and the databases.

In the next sections you find a remind of the description of the structure of the database, the description of the repository of documents, and, the implementation on the MAP and filters for retrieving information on the database. It is possible to access the map at:

www.opendoors.cnr.it

2. The database structure

The Open DOORS database contains three entities, which are “Platform”, “Stakeholder” and “Law”. Each one is described according to a set of attributes specified in the schema which follows. The three entities also represent the three kinds of filters for searching information connected to the Sharing economy.

Figure 1: Description of E-R of the Open DOORS database

2.1 Visualization

The databases of platforms, stakeholders and laws are visualised on a map (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Visualization in the different areas

With the orange circle are visualised the platforms (with the areas where they operate); the laws and regulations are identified in green. Stakeholders are identified by the circle in blue. The number in each circle indicates the number of platforms, or laws or stakeholders that are in the database in the area where the circle is located. Information related to specific resources (meaning for example for a specific platform) can be visualised clicking on a circle, and then selecting one of the platforms of interest (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Visualising information related to specific resources

More information on the specific platform can be visualised selecting the option “details” (see Figure 3). In Figure 4 you see an example of information details such as Name of the platform, Description, Creation data, Web address, Notes, Service cost, Type of operator, Business sectors, Countries where the platform provide its services.

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VizEat

Description:
 VizEat is a global community of people who share great meals and unforgettable moments. We connect hosts and guests from all over the world to experience new flavors and meet new people, whether you're visiting a foreign country or if you're a local looking to get off the beaten path. If you're looking to enjoy a new cuisine, perhaps even a new culture and all the associated dishes, then VizEat is for you.

Creation date:
 01/03/2018

Web Address:
<https://www.vizeat.com/>

Notes:
 World wide

Service Cost:
 VizEat is totally free of charge, whether you register as a host or as a guest. If you want to host people at your home, all you need is a little bit of time and a dash of imagination to post your unique meal online once you've signed up. Hosts are free to establish the price of the meal that they provide. This amount should include the cost of ingredients, as well as the amount for hospitality. In consideration for the use of VizEat's online marketplace and platform, VizEat charges Service Fees. This Service Fees is paid by the guests. For example, if an host wants to reserve a brunch in Paris that costs 25 euros, she'll pay a total of 28 euros and 75 cents.

Business Model:
 CONSUMER_TO_CONSUMER

Operator Type:
 Company

Business Sector:
 Food

Countries:
 EESTI, NEDERLAND, ΕΛΛΑΔΑ (ELLADA), БЪЛГАРИЯ (BULGARIA), FRANCE, SLOVENIJA, BELGIQUE-BELGIË, SLOVENSKO, POLSKA, LIETUVA, LUXEMBOURG, MAGYARORSZÁG, MALTA, SVERIGE, ČESKÁ REPUBLIKA, LATVIJA, ITALIA, UNITED KINGDOM, SUOMI / FINLAND, ÖSTERREICH, IRLAND, HRVATSKA, KYΠΡΟΣ (KYPROS), PORTUGAL, ROMÂNIA, DEUTSCHLAND, DANMARK, ESPAÑA.

Scriveri qui per eseguire la ricerca

19:24
 06/06/2018

Figure 4: Visualization of the information details (an example for a platform)

2.2 Filter and Search

Each user can access the database information filtering by: Business Model, Business Sector, Type of Operator.

Figure 5: Filtering

Figure 6: Filtering by Business model and Business sector

Figure 7: Filtering by Operator

For example if you are interested in platforms which adopt a business model that is “Business_2_Business” you can activate the filter as in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Example of the use of the Business_2_Business filter for platforms

Each person connected to the Open DOORS database can search for Stakeholders, Platforms and Laws. This can be done selecting the option “New search by textual content”. In particular, each search can be done specifying the worlds in the different descriptors (i.e. Service Offered Description, Operator Business Name,...etc.)

The screenshot shows the 'Stakeholders' search form with the following fields:

- Service Offered Description**: service_offered_description
- Operator Business Name**: operator_business_name
- Email**: email
- Contact Name**: contact_name
- Family Name**: family_name
- Phone**: phone
- Web Address**: web_address

Figure 9: Search by textual content. The case of stakeholders

3. What a registered user can do?

3.1 Visualise or upload info in the database

If a user is registered and login in the database system, s/he can visualise the map and information of the database filtering or searching them. Each one can directly access a table containing the set of platforms, stakeholders and laws collected. Moreover, uploading information about new platforms on the sharing and collaborative economy can be directly done by people registered in the platform (in the respect of the European law on privacy and data protection) selecting the option “Create new”.

ID	Creation Date	Name	Description	Service Cost	Notes	Web Address	Type of operator	Business Sector	Countries where the service is available	Business Model	Edit	Delete
1	01/03/2018	Scoterino	Scoterino matches drivers with people wanting to hitch a ride, helping locals avoid public transport and giving tourists another way to see the sights	see the platform	none	www.scoterino.it	Company	Car sharing/ transportation	ITALIA	CONSUMER_TO_CONSUMER	Edit	Delete
2	01/03/2018	iBarter	iBarter offers an online platform from where to quickly and easily form relationships with other companies. iBarter is a community of companies, like you, that buy and sell without the use of cash, but using a complementary currency, the iBcredit (1 iBcredit = 1 Euro) iBarter is much more than just a currency. It is a way of unlocking the untapped potential of your business, reduce unproductivity and take advantage of warehouse stock. You are connected with qualified and reliable entrepreneurs, like you. Sell the goods that a company produces and buy what it needs online: it is an alternative showcase to attract potential new clients. It is possible to buy what the company needs at the cost of products rather than with money."	Companies exchange their goods and pay VAT on the estimated value of the exchanged goods and service	none	https://www.ibarter.com/	Company	e-barter	ITALIA, ESPAÑA	BUSINESS_TO_BUSINESS	Edit	Delete
3	01/03/2018	Airbnb	Airbnb is an online community marketplace that connects people looking to rent their homes with people who are looking for accommodations. It includes hosts and travelers' unused spaces, and travelers search for and book accommodations in 192 countries worldwide.	Airbnb takes a 3% service fee from the host for each reservation to cover the cost of processing the transaction. This fee is in addition to the 6-12% paid for guest service fees Read more: The Pros and Cons of Using Airbnb Investopedia http://www.investopedia.com/articles/personal-finance/032814/pros-and-cons-using-airbnb.asp#zz4rLccP7z8 Follow us: Investopedia on Facebook	World wide	www.airbnb.com	Company	Accommodation (Apartment/House Renting...)	EL/IT/AF/HR (BULGARIA), ÖSTERREICH, POLSKA, LATVIJA, LIETUVA, NEDERLAND, DANMARK, MAGYARORSZÁG, ESPAÑA, BELGIQUE-BELGIE, SUOMI / FINLAND, LUXEMBOURG, PORTUGAL, SVEVENSKE, ITALIA	CONSUMER_TO_CONSUMER	Edit	Delete

Figure 10: Uploading info in the database

You can therefore fill in information of the platform that you want to share in the database in the template (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Uploading new info

3.2 Repository of websites and document

A repository of documents and website relevant for the sharing and collaborative economy was also defined where each actor can upload a document a website, and can find documents or websites shared by other actors is available.

It is possible to access the repository selecting the option “Sharing Economy Documents and Websites” (see Figure 12)

Figure 12: Accessing Sharing Economy Documents and Websites

Figure 13: Searching, collecting and deleting documents and Website

Once logged in each one can search the document or the website specifying a topic.

A user can also upload a new file or a website choosing the file to upload or entering the URL of the website. Finally, each one can delete files or websites previously uploaded. (Each one can only delete files or websites that s/he uploaded, but cannot delete files or URLs that other people collected).

4. Conclusions

A map of resources has been built during the activities of the project Open DOORS. It is an interactive and dynamic map of resources which will follow the MedShare network activities.

Indeed the map facilitates the identification of resources (i.e. platforms, stakeholders and laws) per geographical area. Moreover a collection of documents and websites is also integrated.

These resources can be added by people who get registered to this system. In particular, people and organization can also register themselves in the database of stakeholders. This is also important as an action for the life of the MedShare network.